

INVESTIGATION OF THE DELAMINATION BEHAVIOR ON CARBON FIBER TAPE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

M. Akamatsu¹, T. Ohori¹, T. Hayashi¹ and J. Takahashi¹

¹Department of Systems Innovation, School of Engineering, The University of Tokyo
7-3-1 Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113-8656, Japan
Email: akamatsu-mikio@cfrtp.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp

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ABSTRACT

These days the demand of CFRTP has been growing for application of lightweight automobiles and to achieve the wide usage of CFRTP, designing policy for composite materials should be established. Numerical methods using FE simulation have been researched by researchers up to now, and material selection is one of the solution of composite designing. CTT material is in the spotlight now for its isotropic properties, high formability and so on, and CTT is expected to be the suitable material for actual structural products. UT-CTT made of ultra-thin tapes is now on developing and its detailed mechanical properties should be verified for more application. This study focuses on the fracture behaviour and rigidity of CTT in curved section. L-shaped specimens of UT-CTT were manufactured to conduct tensile tests for observing delamination and load curves. The tests showed the advantage of CTT materials that delamination is less likely to occur in small curved section in CTT, compared to UD materials. FE simulations expressed delamination in L-shaped specimen in a simple way and the strength of CTT was verified as 21 MPa. Load-displacement curves of CTT doesn't agree between tests and simulations and more study is needed to realize the ideal stiffness of CTT curved structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

As the ideal material for mass produced lightweight automobiles, CFRTPs (carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics) have recently been paid attention to, because of its advantage in fast molding cycle, welding and recyclability compared to conventional CFRTPs (carbon fiber reinforced thermosettings). CFRTP application leads to reduction of energy use and solution of some environmental issue such as global warming. Recent years CFRTPs have been radically developed by Japanese research projects [1], and are expected to be studied globally in the future.

To realize the wide application of CFRTP in society, novel structural designing method for composite materials is to be established, considering the characteristics of CFRTP such as anisotropy, delamination and so on. Especially designing complicated structures with curved sections have been a concerning issue, since carbon fibers tend not to be aligned straight at the curved section, which reduces the rigidity of the structure. Delamination is more likely to occur at curved section by a simple loading. Therefore, many researchers have studied the fracture of CFRP hat-shaped tubes [2] or relatively simple curved structure such as L-shaped specimen [3]-[5].

Along with this trend, CTTs (chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics), one of composite materials called discontinuous fiber reinforced materials, have developed in these days. CTTs are the materials made of randomly oriented carbon fiber tapes, which realize in-plane isotropy and high formability. Thus CTTs are expected to be applied mainly to the complicated structural products.

This study deals with L-shaped CTT specimen and aims to verify the mechanical behaviour of CTT curved structure by tensile tests and FE simulations. CTT's stiffness and delamination strength are mainly discussed, compared with UD (uni-directional) materials. Through the discussions this study aims to show the advantage of CTTs for structures and contribute to the establishment of CFRTP application policies.

2 MATERIALS

This study deals with UD material and CTT material. For UD specimens, prepreg sheet produced by Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd. was used. The prepreg sheet is composed of carbon fiber TR50S and polypropylene (PP) as matrix resin. Its fiber volume fraction is 45%. UD L-shaped specimen was manufactured by laminating 25 plies of the UD prepreg sheets through heat and cool compression molding. For CTT specimens, ultra-thin UD prepreg sheet was used. Ultra-thin UD prepreg sheet was provided by the Industrial Technology Center of Fukui Prefecture. UT (ultra-thin)-CTT specimen was manufactured by the compression molding as well, while chopped tapes were randomly oriented in the specimen. Polyamide (PA 6) was used as matrix resin. Tape size was 5 mm in width and 18 mm in length. The thickness of ultra-thin UD prepreg sheet is 44 μm , which is thinner than conventional UD prepreg sheet and is expected to produce lower scatter of experiments. The image of UD specimen and UT-CTT specimen are shown in Figure 1, and the dimension of each specimen is shown in Table 1 respectively.

Figure 1: Image of UD specimen (left) and CTT specimen (right).

		UD specimen	CTT specimen
Length of straight section	[mm]	60	60
Width	[mm]	15	35
Thickness	[mm]	2	2
Inner radius of curved section	[mm]	10, 15, 20	10, 15

Table 1: Dimension of L-shaped specimen.

3 METHODOLOGY

This part explains the methodology of L-shaped specimen tensile test and its FE simulation.

3.1 L-shaped specimen tensile test

Tensile test of L-shaped specimen is a simple method using general testing machine, to observe the fracture of curved structure. Tensile tests were conducted in this study in order to investigate the fracture patterns and to measure load curves.

A specimen was set in testing machine, fixed with special jigs as shown in left side of Figure 2 and right side of Figure 2 shows the condition and the dimension around the jigs. A specimen was pulled at 1 mm/min in velocity. Curved section was painted in white so that delamination was able to be clearly observed.

Applied load and stroke were measured at the crossheads. In this study, load-stroke curves were used to verify the schematic fracture behaviour of UD and CTT specimen. For comparison between experiments and simulations, load-displacement curves were used. Displacement in specimen was defined as follows (Figure 3). Two sets of points were marked in specimen as Point A (located at 15 mm from the edge of the jigs) and Point B (located at 5 mm from the edge of the jigs). The distance between A_1 and A_2 before starting a test was measured by a measure vertically set beside the specimen and defined as L_{a0} , while the distance during a test is defined as L_a , and displacement ΔA was defined

as below:

$$\Delta A = L_a - L_{a0} \quad (1)$$

For Point B, ΔB was defined the same way. Tests were recorded by camera and the displacement at each point was measured with eye on the image. Sampling time was 30 seconds. Load-displacement curves were gained by these measured load and displacement.

Figure 2: Whole image of L-shaped specimen tensile test (left) and the dimension of jig (right).

Figure 3: Displacement measuring method.

3.2 Condition of FE simulation

Simulation of L-shaped specimen tensile test was conducted with FE model shown in Figure 4. The objectives were to compare the stiffness and delamination strength of realistic curved structure, with the model based on the mechanical properties from coupon specimens.

The components of L-shaped specimen were composed of solid elements since solid element calculates stresses in three direction, including out-of-plane direction stress which is supposed to cause delamination. Delamination strength was defined as out-of-plane tensile strength and failure mechanism was based on maximum stress theory in calculation.

As shown in Figure 4, the model of L-shaped specimen was 1/4 part of the actual shape. The number of mesh in out-of-plane direction was 10, which was enough to accurately calculate the stresses and loads. The part of specimen fixed with jigs was constrained rigid body displayed in red color and velocity was set at the tip of rigid body. The tip of rigid body was regarded as the rotating bearing of a jig and corresponding degree of freedom was set at the point.

Radioss block was used as solver and COMPOSITE SOLID MATERIAL (law14) was selected as material card in the solver. The mechanical properties of UD and CTT were set as shown in Table 2. Elastic modulus of UD specimen (asterisk are added) were verified by Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd. and those of CTT specimen (double asterisks are added) were from the tests in our laboratory.

Figure 4: Image of FE model.

Engineering constant		UD	CTT
E_1	[GPa]	101*	48.0**
E_2	[GPa]	4.61*	48.0**
E_3	[GPa]	4.00	2.60
ν_{12}	–	0.34*	0.30
G_{12}	[GPa]	1.63*	18.5
G_{13}	[GPa]	1.00	1.00

Table 1: Mechanical properties set in FE models.

4 RESULTS

This part shows the results of the fracture behaviour of L-shaped specimen tensile test and the calculation in FE simulation. UD material and CTT material are compared in each verification.

4.1 Observation of fracture behavior in tests

Three specimens were tested for each condition to investigate a transition of fracture mode due to inner radius. For UD material, delamination was observed as the initial fracture in specimens of which inner radius were 10 mm and 15 mm. For specimens of which inner radius were 20 mm, compressive fracture was observed as the initial fracture. The images of the fractures on specimens are shown in Figure 5. For all conditions, load applied to the specimen continued to rise after the fracture as shown in Figure 6. This results indicate the high tensile strength of continuous fiber reinforced material, which sustains the structure after fractures.

For CTTs, delamination was observed as the initial fracture in specimens of which inner radius were 10 mm. For specimens of which inner radius were 15 mm, one sample showed delamination, while other two samples showed in-plane tensile fracture at the inside of the curved section. The images of the fractures are shown in Figure 7. Figure 8 shows load-stroke curves of CTT specimens. The small scatter of tests, the characteristic of UT-CTT compared with conventional CTTs, is seen in Figure 8. Specimens with delamination fracture continued to rise its load, while specimens which once failed by tensile fracture finally broke into two pieces after the initial fracture.

According to a study by Wan et al [6], initial fracture mode varies by selecting inner radius of curves section. It is supposed by this study that for UD materials delamination occurs at corners of which inner radius is less than 20 mm, while for CTT materials less than 15 mm. These results indicate that CTTs are suitable materials for structural design with small curved sections.

Figure 5: Delamination (left) and compressive fracture (right) in UD specimen.

Figure 6: Load-stroke curves of UD specimens.

Figure 7: Delamination (left) and tensile fracture (right) in CTT specimen.

Figure 8: Load-stroke curves of CTT specimens.

4.2 Comparison between experiments and simulations

The left side of Figure 9 shows the contour diagrams of out-of-plane stress in L-shaped specimen model. Maximum tensile stress locates near the middle part of curved section. Out-of-plane tensile fracture (regarded as delamination) occurs as shown in the right side of Figure 9 when tensile stress in one mesh reaches its tensile strength. This modelling method has a big advantage that delamination can be expressed without verifying the location of the fracture in the components beforehand, and can be applied easily to complicated structures. Comparing with the maximum load in tests gives the prediction of delamination strength. In this study, delamination strength of UD specimens was predicted as 19 MPa, and 21 MPa for CTT specimens respectively.

With load-displacement curves, the stiffness were compared between tests and simulations. For UD specimens, the load in simulation was higher than in tests when inner radius was small (Figure 10). The cause can be explained with images taken by X-rays CT scans before conducting tests (Figure 11). There was resin-rich area outside of curved section. The area tends to be larger in smaller curved radius, which indicates the difficulty of perfect manufacturing of UD material in small radius corners. For CTT specimens, the load in simulation was higher than those in tests (Figure 12). Figure 13 shows the images of CTT specimen by X-rays CT scans and there was no significant defect in the specimen. Possible cause was the degradation of matrix resin. The optimal method to manufacture CTT L-shaped specimens was not established and the heating condition was supposed to have a bad influence on PA 6. Additionally, some mechanical properties such as out-of-plane Young's modulus or Shear modulus have not verified strictly by tests yet. Young's modulus for compression stress might be lower than that for tensile stress. It is necessary to clarify the proper molding condition for CTT and the unknown parameters as soon as possible.

Figure 9: Stress contour diagram (left) and delamination (right) in FE simulation.

Figure 10: Load-displacement curves of UD specimens at Point A and Point B.

Figure 11: Images of the side of UD specimens by X-rays CT scans.

Figure 12: Load-displacement curves of CTT specimens at Point A and Point B.

Figure 13: Images of the side of CTT specimens by X-rays CT scans.

5 CONCLUSIONS

CTT material is one of desirable materials for designing complicated CFRTP structures. This study discussed CTT curved specimens and verified the fracture and stiffness compared with UD specimens. By conducting tensile tests and observations, it was proved that UT-CTT is the more suitable material to be applied in curved structures than continuous fiber reinforced materials, for the fluidity and formability of ultra-thin tapes. Moreover, delamination behavior and load-stroke curves showed the same tendency in CTT and UD specimens. Therefore almost the same condition of FE simulation was applied to both of materials. In FE simulation, delamination was expressed by out-of-plane tensile fracture and it enabled to express delamination without verifying the location of the initial fracture. The discrepancy of the load in UD specimens between tests and simulation was verified by X-rays observation and UD materials were proved to have difficulty being made tidy in small curved sections. For CTTs, it is necessary to verify the factors degrading the properties and more researches on CTT materials contribute toward the wide usage of CFRTPs in society.

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